

The inhibition of atmospheric aqueous phase autoxidation of sulfur dioxide by volatile organic compounds : Benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene, *p*-xylene, *n*-hexane and dichloromethane

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Manuscript received 06 January 2017, revised 17 February 2017, accepted 21 February 2017

Abstract : This comprehensive study examines the effect of seven volatile organic compounds (VOCs), viz. benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene, *p*-xylene, *n*-hexane, dichloromethane. The disappearance of aqueous sulfur(IV), [S^{IV}], follows a first order kinetics.

The nature of the dependence of k_{obs} on the concentration of inhibitor, [Inh], was defined by eq. (A).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 / (1 + B [\text{Inh}]) \quad (\text{A})$$

where k_0 and k_{obs} are the first order rate constant in the absence and the presence of VOCs, respectively and B is an empirical inhibition parameter. Among VOCs, whereas *p*-xylene, *n*-hexane and dichloromethane had no effect, *o*-xylene and *m*-xylene displayed strong inhibition. Addition of benzene and toluene resulted in the introduction of induction period indicating a very high value of B . The experimental B values, are $(1.4 \pm 0.83) \times 10^4$ and $(2.33 \pm 1.4) \times 10^4$ L mol⁻¹ for *o*-xylene and *m*-xylene, respectively.

Keywords : Sulfur(IV), sulfur dioxide, oxidation, hydrocarbons, inhibition, sulfate radical anions, kinetics, VOCs.

Introduction

The aqueous phase atmospheric oxidation of sulfur dioxide by oxygen is a significant contributor to acid rain. This has led to numerous studies and details are available in reviews and books¹⁻⁵. The oxidation of dissolved sulfur dioxide, hereafter referred to as sulfur(IV), follows a radical mechanism, which involves sulfoxy radicals, viz. SO₃⁻, SO₄⁻ and SO₅⁻ as intermediates¹⁻⁵. Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)⁶⁻⁸, which are an integral part of the air atmosphere, inhibit the autoxidation of sulfur(IV) via scavenging of sulfate radical anions, SO₄⁻ (1-3)⁹⁻¹⁴.

To understand the atmospheric chemistry of VOCs-sulfur(IV)-O₂ system, several studies have been reported. These studies on aqueous SO₂ autoxidation⁹⁻²⁰ have shown

the inhibition kinetics, in general, to be described by rate law (4).

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k_0[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/(1 + B [\text{Inh}]) \quad (4)$$

where k_0 is the first order rate constant in the absence of inhibitor, B is an empirical inhibition parameter and [Inh] is the concentration of inhibitor.

Prior to our work on VOCs-sulfur(IV)-O₂ system, effect of VOCs was examined on this system in presence of a catalyst⁹⁻¹⁶. These studies on VOC effect do not mimic the real atmospheric situations. Keeping usefulness to atmospheric chemistry in view, we undertook exhaustive studies of VOC-effect on uncatalyzed sulfur(IV) autoxidation in which no catalyst was added from outside.

The presence of large number of VOCs having variety of functional groups demanded a concerted effort to study the effect of VOCs of each type such as aliphatic, heterocyclic and aromatic hydrocarbons, their substituted derivatives including such as alcohols, aldehyde, ketones,

esters, ethers, nitro derivatives etc. The systematic detailed studies on uncatalyzed VOCs-sulfur(IV)-O₂ system by Dhayal *et al.*^{17,18} and Meena *et al.*¹⁹ found the inhibition parameter, *B*, to be related to the rate constant, *k*_{Inh}, for the reaction (5) by eq. (6).

where VOC[•] represents a radical.

$$B = (0.9 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-3} \times k_{\text{Inh}} \quad (6)$$

The inhibition action of a VOC in S^{IV} autoxidation depends on its *B* value, which in turn depends on its *k*_{Inh}.

Some work on the effect of hydrocarbons on sulfur(IV) autoxidation has been reported. However, in all these studies chosen for studying the effect of hydrocarbons, autoxidation was catalyzed by manganese(II)^{15,16} and palladium(II)²⁰. The effect of VOCs and some hydrocarbons on autoxidation of S^{IV} in presence of automobile diesel exhaust particles by Meena *et al.*¹⁹ has been reported recently.

A literature survey revealed that *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes, toluene, benzene²², *n*-hexane²³, dichloromethane²⁴ are found in atmosphere but their role on dissolved SO₂ autoxidation has not been studied so far. To fill this gap, we have examined the effect of these VOCs and report results in this paper.

Experimental

In all, the effect of seven VOCs has been studied. Most of these compounds were liquids and some were solids. The compounds were used as received. Care taken to use only recently purchased samples. The experimental procedure for studying the kinetics of the oxidation of dissolved sulfur dioxide, sulfur(IV), by oxygen was exactly the same as described earlier^{17,18,19a,20,21} and is briefly given here.

Sodium sulfite used was of reagent grade and its solution was prepared in double-distilled water. The reactions were conducted in 0.15-L Erlenmeyer flasks, open to air to allow the passage of atmospheric oxygen. The flask was placed in a beaker, which had an inlet at the lower part and an outlet at the upper part for circulating thermostated water for maintaining the desired temperature, 25.0 ± 0.1 °C. The reaction was initiated by adding the desired volume of standard Na₂SO₃ solution to the

reaction mixture containing desired amount of distilled water. The reaction mixture was stirred continuously and magnetically at 1600 ± 100 rpm to allow the passage of atmospheric oxygen and to prevent the reaction from becoming oxygen mass transfer controlled²⁰. The kinetics was studied without use of any buffer to avoid introduction of impurities^{18,19a}.

The kinetics was followed by withdrawing the aliquot samples periodically and titrating the unreacted sulfur(IV) iodometrically in slightly acidic medium as described earlier. The reproducibility of the replicate measurements was generally better than ±10%. All calculations were performed in MS Excel.

The oxidation of sulfur(IV) by O₂ was found to be consistent with eq. (7).

Results

Rate law :

In inhibition studies with hydrocarbons and their derivatives, the nature of disappearance of sulfur(IV), in the absence of the inhibitors, was first order, as defined by eq. (8).

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = R_0 = k_0 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (8)$$

where, *R*₀, *k*₀ and [S^{IV}] are the initial rate, first order rate constant and concentrations of sulfur(IV), respectively in the absence of VOCs. In the presence of inhibitors too, the disappearance of sulfur(IV) remained first order in conformity with eq. (9).

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = R_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (9)$$

where, *R*_{obs} and *k*_{obs} are the initial rate and the first order rate constant, respectively in the presence of VOCs. *k*_{obs} were determined from log [S^{IV}] versus time plots (Table 1). Some representative first order plots are in Fig. 1. As in previous studies¹⁷⁻²¹, the nature of inhibition was characterized by eq. (10).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 / (1 + B [\text{Inh}]) \quad (10)$$

In accordance with eq. (10), the plots between 1/*k*_{obs} versus [Inh] were straight lines. Some such plots are in Fig. 2. In each case, from the ratio of slope (= *B*/*k*₀) and intercept (= 1/*k*₀) of these linear plots, the values of *B* was determined (Table 2).

Table 1. The selected values of rate constant, k_{obs} , for *o*- and *m*-xylenes at pH = 8.15 and 25 °C

Compound	[Inh] (mol/L)	[S ^{IV}] (mol/L)	k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0	2×10^{-3}	3.5×10^{-4}
	4.14×10^{-5}	2×10^{-3}	1.96×10^{-4}
	8.28×10^{-5}	2×10^{-3}	9.6×10^{-5}
	1.24×10^{-4}	2×10^{-3}	1.30×10^{-4}
	1.65×10^{-4}	2×10^{-3}	9.7×10^{-5}
<i>m</i> -Xylene	0	2×10^{-3}	3.5×10^{-4}
	4.14×10^{-5}	2×10^{-3}	2.77×10^{-5}
	8.28×10^{-5}	2×10^{-3}	2.4×10^{-5}
	4.14×10^{-5}	2×10^{-3}	2.19×10^{-5}

Fig. 1. The first order plots for the autoxidation of [S^{IV}] in the presence and the absence of *o*-xylene at pH = 8.15 and 25 °C.

The effect of two aliphatic hydrocarbons, *n*-hexane and dichloromethane, was examined. Interestingly, both were without any significant effect (Fig. 1). Aromatic hydrocarbons selected for study were benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene and *p*-xylene, out of which *p*-xylene was without any significant effect within the experimental uncertainty of the present rate measurements (Table 1).

Benzene and toluene had a severe rate inhibiting effect, so much so that during the study period of two hour

Fig. 2. The plot of $1/k_i$ versus [Inhibitor], pH = 8.15 at $t = 25$ °C.

no reaction occurred, showing *B* to have a very high value. Such an induction period, during which no reaction occurred, has been observed in the presence of benzene and toluene in Pd^{II} and Os^{VIII}-catalyzed S^{IV} oxidation¹⁴.

Discussion

The major cause of inhibition of sulfur(IV) autoxidation is believed to be the intervention of VOCs in the sulfoxy radical chain and the scavenging of sulfate radical anions. Based on the work of Aleya and Backstrom²⁵, Hayon *et al.*²⁶, Huie and Neta²⁷, Pausik-Bronikowaska *et al.*⁹, Mudgal *et al.*²⁰ *etc.*, the result of this study can be explained by the mechanism (11–18).

Mechanism :

(1) Initiation

where M^{n+} is trace metal ion present as impurity.

(2) Propagation

(3) Oxidation

(4) Termination

Based on the work Ziajka and Pasiuk-Bronikowska⁹, Mudgal *et al.*²⁰ and Dhayal *et al.*¹⁸ the rate law (10) from the mechanism (1–8) could be derived.

Table 2. *B* values for aromatic and aliphatic hydrocarbons and their derivatives at pH = 8.15 and 25 °C

Hydrocarbon	Physical state	Inhibition parameter, <i>B</i> , (L mol ⁻¹)	Solubility/Miscibility (g/L)	<i>k</i> _{Inh} (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
Benzene, C ₆ H ₆	Liquid	In presence of 2 × 10 ⁻³ mol L ⁻¹ benzene, no reaction during study period, 3 h	1.84 (30 °C)	(6.4 ± 2.5) × 10 ⁹ (Ref. 29)
Toluene, C ₇ H ₈	Liquid	In presence of 2 × 10 ⁻³ mol L ⁻¹ toluene, no reaction during study period, 2 h	0.53 (30 °C)	(1.3 ± 0.6) × 10 ⁹ (Ref. 30)
<i>o</i> -Xylene, C ₈ H ₁₀	Liquid	(1.4 ± 0.83) × 10 ⁴	Immiscible	Estimated 1.6 × 10 ⁷
<i>m</i> -Xylene, C ₈ H ₁₀	Liquid	(2.33 ± 1.4) × 10 ⁴	Immiscible	Estimated 2.6 × 10 ⁷
<i>p</i> -Xylene, C ₈ H ₁₀	Liquid	No effect	Immiscible	(2.7 ± 0.9) × 10 ⁹ (Ref. 30)
<i>n</i> -Hexane, C ₆ H ₁₄	Liquid	No effect	0.013 (20 °C)	–
Dichloromethane, CH ₂ Cl ₂	Liquid	No effect	15.8 (30 °C)	–

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 / \{1 + \alpha k_{\text{Inh}} [\text{Inh}] / k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}]\} \quad (19)$$

The experimental rate law (10) is in agreement with the derived rate law (19) through eq. (20).

$$B = \{\alpha / k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}]\} k_{\text{Inh}} \quad (20)$$

Assuming the term $\{\alpha / k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}]\}$ to be constant, the eq. (20) indicates *B* to be a function of *k*_{Inh} primarily.

Now, we discuss the results of inhibition effect of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons. As reported previously^{14,19a,28}, both benzene and toluene have a severe inhibition effect. Apparently, *B* value is so high that there is no reaction during the period of study, 2 h, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The effect of toluene/benzene on autoxidation of [S^{IV}] at pH = 8.15 and 25 °C.

This requires value of *k*_{Inh} for both benzene and toluene to be high. Indeed, it is true and *k*_{Inh} value for benzene²⁹ is (6.4 ± 2.5) × 10⁹ and for toluene³⁰ is (1.3 ± 0.6) × 10⁹ L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹. Accordingly, use of benzene *k*_{Inh} value

in eq. (21) proposed by Dhayal *et al.*¹⁸ yields high *B* value of ~5.7 × 10⁶ L mol⁻¹.

$$B = (9 \pm 2) \times 10^{-4} \times k_{\text{Inh}} \quad (21)$$

Hydrocarbons react with SO₄⁻ via H-abstraction pathway as shown in reaction (22).

The effect of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes on sulfur(IV) autoxidation is interesting. Whereas, *o*- and *m*-xylene have strong inhibiting effect, the *p*-xylene has no effect. The non-inhibiting effect of *p*-xylene may be explained as follows. A closer examination of their structures shows that in *p*-xylene, for H-abstraction all available sites for SO₄⁻ attack are adjacent to substituent CH₃. On the other hand, in case of other two xylenes, hydrogen atoms remote to CH₃ group are available for attack. There appears to be two reasons, among others, for non-inhibition by *p*-xylene. Firstly, the presence of neighboring CH₃ group in *p*-xylene hinders the attack at adjacent secondary H-atom on carbon by SO₄⁻ due to steric effect. The abstraction of secondary H-atom^{31,32} is known to be easier than a primary H-atom from CH₃. Secondly, *o*- and *m*-xylenes both have hydrogen atoms available on secondary carbon atoms remote from CH₃ groups for abstraction by SO₄⁻ radical. *o*- and *m*-xylenes, therefore, scavenge SO₄⁻ radicals efficiently leading to high *B* value.

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The apparent non-inhibition does not indicate that there is no reaction between *p*-xylene and SO_4^- . There are two possibilities. One, possibly the value of k_{Inh} for *p*-xylene- SO_4^- reaction is relatively lower at $\sim 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Such a low value will lead to a low value of $B \sim 10^2$ in accordance with eq. (21). According to eq. (10), such a low value B would lead to an inhibition of about 10%. This being within the experimental uncertainty would not manifest itself. Two, k_{Inh} may be high but the structure of radical formed in step (22) may be such that it reacts with O_2 to form a reactive peroxide, which oxidizes sulfur(IV) at nearly the same rate as sulfate radical. Similar non-inhibition, in Mn^{II} -catalyzed S^{IV} oxidation in aqueous solution by malic (pH = 9, $k_{\text{Inh}} = 1.5 \times 10^6 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and malonic (pH = 9, $k_{\text{Inh}} = 5.5 \times 10^6 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) acids has been reported by Grgic *et al.*³³ despite their k_{Inh} values being relatively higher. No exact reason could be assigned for this behavior³³. It was suggested that there could be additional reaction, which may form peroxy radicals which might oxidize sulfur(IV) and hinder the inhibition.

Among the aliphatic hydrocarbons, *n*-hexane and dichloromethane are without any effect. Aliphatic hydrocarbons, in general, are known to react with SO_4^- radicals relatively much slowly than the aromatic hydrocarbons. For example, the value of k_{Inh} ³³ for C_2H_6 is $7.4 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ as compared to k_{Inh} value of $(6.4 \pm 2.5) \times 10^9 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for C_6H_6 . Because of this, B values for aliphatic hydrocarbons are generally low and sometimes below detection limit.

In case of the inhibition of sulfur(IV) autoxidation by chlorophenols, it has been reported previously that the presence of chlorine as a substituent lowers the inhibition efficiency³⁴. Further, an increase in the number of chlorine substituent decreases the inhibition efficiency further. In line with this, in our study dichloromethane shows

no inhibition, which might be due to low B and k_{Inh} values.

Application to atmospheric chemistry :

In real atmospheric situations, the effectiveness of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons and their derivatives as inhibitors may be described by eq. (23)¹⁸.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 / (1 + \{\sum B_i [\text{Inh}]_i\} / k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}]) \quad (23)$$

where k_{Inh} and $[\text{Inh}]_i$ are the rate constant of *i*-th VOC with SO_4^- and the concentration of *i*-th VOC, respectively.

The reaction between sulfate ion radical and a contaminant has two important implications in environmental chemistry. One, the inhibition of SO_2 -autoxidation will decrease the rate of oxidation SO_2 by O_2 in atmospheric aqueous systems and hence increase residence time of SO_2 . This controls the acidification of atmospheric waters. Simultaneously, this reaction results in the degradation of atmospheric volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which are toxic and pollute air, soil and water^{18,35}. Thus, the reaction (18) acts as sink for the oxidation and removal of VOCs from the atmosphere.

The reaction of SO_4^- radicals with VOCs is the basis of Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) for the degradation and removal of contaminants from water and soil³⁶. In AOPs sulfate radical ions are produced by action of heat, metal ion catalysts, photolysis, etc., on peroxydisulfate/peroxymonosulfate systems. SO_4^- radicals have been found to degrade efficiently the pharmaceuticals³⁷, phenolic compounds³⁸, herbicides³⁹, antibiotics, etc. in the remediation of contaminated groundwater and soil, etc.⁴⁰. This subject has been reviewed very recently⁴¹. The magnitude of B value of an organic compound is an indicator of its ability to react with the contaminant and get destroyed. Higher is the value of B , faster and easier would be its degradation by an AOP.

Conclusion

This study suggests that aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons and their derivatives, which are found in atmosphere and wherever their concentrations are sizable, would inhibit sulfur(IV) autoxidation. Consequently, these will increase the lifetime of aqueous SO_2 and decrease the rate of sulfur(IV)-autoxidation reaction. Further, the organic inhibitors would also undergo degradation owing to their reactions with SO_4^- radicals.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by SERB/DST project and CSIR JRF.

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